

Micro fluidic chip that able to purify a Viral Nucleic Acid without any chemical reactions.

Umair Masood

DNA extraction is a method to purify a DNA by utilizing physical or chemical techniques from a sample isolating DNA from cell proteins, and other cell parts. To extract DNA the four stages all together are Lysis, separation, precipitation, and purification. Mostly in the DNA extraction of any species plant animal or microbes we can breaking the cell wall or cell membrane separated DNA from protein or other cellular materials cleaning the DNA and confirm the presence of DNA but viral nucleic acid extraction is a critical usually phenol-chloroform and alkaline lysis method are used in order to purify a nucleic acid but this method is not reliable even some time you can repeat your purification again and again due to the presence of some other DNA or proteins which can cause a contamination and viral DNA is not purify completely.

Purify a viral nucleic acid without any chemical reactions are based on nylon protein base receptor in which virus attaches to the surface of the nylon protein base receptor and DNA enter to the chip. Nylon protein based receptor method is one step method or protocol simply you can load your viral sample into the chip the virus start binding to the receptor and injected their DNA directly into the chip.

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